
PRAGMATICS OF OFFICIAL STYLE AS A TOOL FOR DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN BUSINESS LINGUISTICS

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The article aims to identify, describe, systematize, and compare linguistic means expressing communicative and pragmatic meaning in determining their composition, semantics, and functions in the genres of law, order, and international agreement. Furthermore, it defines the specifics of the conditions of communication in the business sphere; revealed the communicative specificity of stereotyped role manifestations and speech behavior in terms of the functioning of oral and written genres, characteristic for speech communication in the professional sphere.

When a diplomat says *yes*, he means 'perhaps';

When he says *perhaps*, he means 'no';

When he says *no*, he is not a diplomat. – *Voltaire*

These lines – also attributed to H. L. Mencken and Carl Jung – may or may not be fair to diplomats, but are surely correct in reminding us that more is involved in what one communicates than what one literally says; more is involved in what one means than the standard, conventional meaning of the words one uses.

The growing interest in the functioning of linguistic units in the speech of different spheres of activity and increasing attention to the human factor in the language predetermined the choice of the topic of this study - the means of expressing communicative-pragmatic meaning in an official speech.

The current stage in the development of linguistic thought is characterized by a turn towards a communicative-pragmatic approach, which involves the study of the relationship between linguistic units and their various associations with the extra-linguistic situation of communication in a certain sphere of human activity. This approach allows us to consider a wide range of issues related to the "talking"

subject, the addressee of speech, their interaction, as well as the context of communication.

In recent decades, the development of a communicative-pragmatic approach has led to a shift in the attention of linguists from the author of the speech (the "speaking" subject) to the second participant in communication, the addressee. In this regard, it becomes a relevant consideration of the communicative and pragmatic meaning of statements.⁴⁸

Under the communicative-pragmatic meaning, the authors mean the value associated with the implementation of the formal, meaningful, and linguistic orientation of the statements to the addressee in a particular situation of communication. Such an understanding of communicative-pragmatic meaning predetermined the interest in the address of the utterance and the means of its implementation in the official speech.

The study of the addressee's problem is carried out within the framework of many linguistic directions (semantic, functional grammatical, pragmatic, sociolinguistic, semiotic, hermeneutic, linguistic, linguodidactic, etc.). The distinction of private objects and subjects of research led to a variety of approaches to the consideration of the addressee (speech recipient, V interlocutor, listener, reader, recipient, interpreter, second communicator, speaker's partner, etc.).⁴⁹

The relevance of this study is determined by the development in modern linguistics of a communicative and pragmatic approach to the study of speech in different spheres of communication; the need to identify and describe the characteristics of lexical and grammatical means and speech organization of official business speech from the perspective of the addressee; the need to develop a way of describing the means of expression of communicative-pragmatic meaning in individual genres; the prospect of studying the genres of official business speech as units of communication; high productivity and social significance of the genres of "law", "order", "international agreement".

The object of this study is the genres of the prescription of formal business writing, functioning in different spheres of business communication as speech works.

⁴⁸ Abdulameer, A.H., Noor, S.N.F.M., & Nasser, W.K. (2019). Systemic functional linguistics of political articles in Eastern and Western online news. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 7(5), 24-31.

⁴⁹ Akkuzova, A., Mankeyev, Z., Akkuzov, A., Kaiyrbekova, U., & Baiymbetova, R. (2018). Some features of the meaning "literary text" in the pragmatolinguistic aspect. *Opción*, 34(85-2), 20-34.

The subject of the research is the means of realization of communicative-pragmatic meaning and their functional features in the genres of "law", "order" and "international agreement".

Official written communication differs from communication in other areas by a number of specific features: firstly, the participants of communication represent a variable circle of subjects of legal relations, including active citizens of the state and their various associations, secondly, communicants are in legal relations, thirdly, communication of the parties is regulated through written registration of codified-legal norms.⁵⁰

The compositional, structural, substantive, semantic, and linguistic design of communicative and pragmatic meanings in the genres of "law", "order", and "international agreement" is predetermined by the communicative situation and, in particular, by the characteristics of the addressing⁵¹.

Lexico-grammatical means the function in the official genres of "law", "order", and "international agreement", which implement the meaning of address in the context of the structure and semantics of a certain genre. In the genres of "law", "order", "international agreement" various types of situations of addressing are made out: in the genre of "law" the situation of self-addressing is presented, in the genre of "order" - the situation of absolute addressing, in the genre of "international agreement" - the situation of reciprocal addressing. Addressing situations are distinguished by the addressee's parameters and the types of addressee relationships. In the genres of "law", "order", and "international agreement" the communicative-pragmatic meaning is realized through a special way of organizing linguistic units in the speech structure of the genre.

According to Austin, the value of the study is in specifics of the realization of communicative-pragmatic meaning in the genres of official written communication; in establishing and describing the basic principles of selection⁵², organization and functioning of linguistic means expressing an address in the genres of prescription; in determining and considering the types of situations of addressing, presented in the genres of "law", "order", "international agreement"; in justifying the dependence of the choice of the lexicogrammatical form of the means of realization of the value, addressed to the criteria of the addressing situation; in identifying and describing the speech structure of prescription genres in a pragmatic aspect. The theoretical significance of the research lies in clarifying the repertoire of language

⁵⁰ Bakhtin, M. M. (1997). The problem of speech genres. Moscow: Russian Dictionaries.

⁵¹ Bogdanov, V. V. (1990). Speech communication: pragmatic and semantic aspects. LGU.

⁵² Austin, J. L. (2004). Performatives are constables. Philosophy of language. Moscow: Editorial URSS..

means of addressing in official genres with respect to the system of means addressed to the modern Russian language, in determining the characteristics of the addressee of formal business writing and in describing its main models, in identifying features of meaningful semantic content and compositional-graphic design of the studied genres from the position of the addressee⁵³.

The presented method of researching the expression of communicative-pragmatic meaning in the genres of a prescription can be used in the study of other official business genres and genres of other fields of communication. The speech structure of the genres of the prescription, in which the direction of the statement "outward" is realized, can be represented as follows: "performative + add-ons or individual statements dependent on it". The presence of two types of components (one constant verbal component and dependent on it verbal-variable components) in the speech structure of the genres of prescription is explained by the fact that the permanent verbal component, formed by the performative verb, expresses the kind of impulse without indicating the action that the addressee must perform⁵⁴ (Kuznetsova, 2002).

Performance verbs require the use of constructions that call this action or actions. An indication of the action(s) is contained in verbal-variable components. Actions prescribed to the addressee are called verbs, the morphological and syntactic representation of which differs depending on the genre - in orders, actions are called infinitive verbs that perform the function of addition, and in laws and international agreements personal and impersonal verb forms that perform the function of predicate offers. In the clauses of the order and the articles of the law and the international treaty, it completes what is not expressed in the lexical meaning of the verbperformative itself. Thus, in the constant verbal component, the idea of impulse is expressed, in the verbal-successive components - the idea of directionality and the idea of action⁵⁵. Each genre is a typical statement, compositional-graphic, the content-thematic and linguistic embodiment of which is determined by the specifics of the sphere of communication.

A communicative-pragmatic approach to the study of formal business genres allows you to explore the features of the implementation of the utterance of the statement at the compositional, structural and contentsemantic levels, to describe the repertoire of means of expression of addressing and the specifics of their

⁵³ Aznabayeva, L.A. (1998). Principles of addressee's speech behavior in conventional communication.

⁵⁴ Kuznetsova, T. V. (2002). Office work (documentation management). Moscow: ZAO «Biznes-shkola «IntelSintez».

44. Lekanta, P. A

⁵⁵ Bolshakov, I. A. (1985). On some linguistic features of business prose. Semiotika i informatika, 26, 24-33. 14.

functioning in individual genres. The considered genres of “law”, “order”, and “international agreement” are genres of prescription, which determines the identity of the expressed meaning of addressing - all studied speech works (documents) are speech actions that regulate the behavior of certain addressees. In identifying communicative and pragmatic meanings in the compositional and structural design of the genres of prescription, the authors proceeded from the traditional division of the speech work into a title (document name) and a part of the text. The genre as an object of research allowed comparing the compositional parts of works of different genres with the distribution of information elements (details of documents) in them, to describe their interweaving and features of the implicit and explicit design of the value of the address. As a result of the analysis of the compositional and structural design of the “law”, “order”, “international agreement” genres, the authors of the article concluded that from the position of the addressee it is advisable to distinguish two blocks, one of which is oriented to the past and the other to the future. In the first block, the communicative situation is shaped by lexical and grammatical means, in the second block, the actions of the addressees are regulated ⁵⁶.

Two blocks are separated by a genre-forming verb, they do not coincide with the compositional parts and are not related to the location of details in documents. The study of the peculiarities of the implementation of communicative and pragmatic meaning in the content-semantic side of the genres “law”, “order”, “international agreement” showed that all the described genres express a will, which is formed as a speech act. The genres “law”, “order”, “international treaty” are performative statements, the lexicogrammatical form of the verb in each genre is caused by the addressing situation .

The stereotype of official speech, on the one hand, and the state-conscious standardization of the content, form, language of individual genres, on the other hand, allows us to describe the repertoire of each genre as accurately as possible. When identifying means of expressing the value of addressing in the genres of "law", "order", and "international agreement" and describing the features of their functioning, there was concluded that the main language tool for the design and updating of communicative -pragmatic meaning in prescription genres is a performative verb, which firstly, is a genreforming tool in the genres in question; secondly, the permanent verbal component of the speech structure of the genres of prescription; thirdly, the main means of expressing the value of addressing, which

⁵⁶ Kryukova, Ye. A. (2003). Language and style of legislation. Doctoral dissertation. Moscow.

functions in the genres of prescription; all other multi-level language tools included in the repertoire of means of expressing the value of addressing acquire this meaning in the context of the genre (against the background of extralinguistic factors).

In the repertoire of the prescriptive official genres, three groups of means can be distinguished, with varying degrees of intensity expressing the value of address:

- A special or specialized means of representing the meaning of address, organizing, actualizing, and shaping the meaning of address, is a performative (represented by a verb or its particular form);

- “Active” means (words and constructions with a modal meaning), expressing the direction of the statement “outward” as a stated wish;

- “Inactive” means (nouns and pronouns with the meaning “person”) denoting the addressee, i.e. vector-pointing statements. The specificity of the communicative-pragmatic meaning of an utterance in the formal written spheres of communication is manifested in the special selection, organization, and functioning of means of language, in the compositional graphical design, and in the content-semantic filling of genres.

Official business genres as statements have a pragmatic meaning and directional function to the addressee in order to induce him to respond (verbal or non-verbal). - Secondly, the genre is considered as a unit of speech communication, and not as a type of text. Consequently, in the genre, which is a "link" in communication, by certain means, its communicative and pragmatic orientation is realized to a certain addressee. The specificity of written communication in the official business sphere lies in the fact that the replica-statement of a lively conversation corresponds to a document of a certain genre.⁵⁷

Documents submitted by various genres, like replicas, can initiate communication (for example, the order for main activities), respond to another document (for example, the order for personnel), record the result of communication (for example, an international agreement as a result of negotiations, the law as a result discussion).

Official written genres are special speech works, the creation, and functioning of which, unlike the genres of other spheres of communication, are dictated not only by traditions of use but also associated with artificial codification by the state . All written official business genres are united by the general concept of

⁵⁷ . Kushneruk, S. P. (2005). Modern documentary text: problems of formation, development and composition. Volgograd: Volgograd Scientific Edition.

“document”. In a peer-reviewed study, a document is considered as a speech work of the official communication sphere, the language design of which is predetermined by a specific way of its creation and functioning. The document, unlike literary, artistic, scientific, and publicistic works, has legal force. The requirements contained in the documents are binding, they are supported and controlled by the state.

This extra-linguistic factor provides the communicative-pragmatic orientation of the official utterance to a specific addressee. A document as a social work assumes the following order of its creation: the existence of a draft document - its editing, obtaining as a result of a document, which, as a rule, is not subject to further changes and functions in the approved form. The stepwise creation of documents will enable repeated (within the allotted time) access to the text for editing, as well as the inclusion of representatives of different stakeholders into the document creation process, which makes the document a collective speech work).⁵⁸

Control over the creation and use of documents consciously conducted by the state, their standardization and unification has led to a limiting degree of the stereotype of written statements in the formal business communication sphere, which is manifested in compositions (availability of a form), in the content (assignment of a document to each genre of the document) and in language units (use of cliché language forms) of the genre. The document as a special way of organizing writing in the official communication sphere assumes a specific formulation of the utterance. The compositional construction of documents is based on a constructive principle, which is based on a legally fixed list of details (document information elements), which are variably represented in the composition of documents of various genres.⁵⁹

The compositional and graphic design of documents of different genres considers the addressee's factor. The pre-text part, including the details of the “Document type's name”, “Title”, is the maximally minimized text content. These details are specific signals for the addressee, indicating the subject sphere of communication. The text of the documents of various genres of prescription is divided into an establishing part, which reveals the causes, goals, and objectives, which served as the basis for issuing a document or justifies the need for its

⁵⁸ .Rasulov Z.I. Activation of Information Fragments in the Text. Development and Innovations in Science. Dutch International Scientific Online Conference. Issue13, Part 2. –Amsterdam, Netherlands: AID, 2022. –P. 36-40. <http://econferences.ru/index.php/dis/article/view/427/372>

⁵⁹ Kuznetsova, T. V. (2002). Office work (documentation management). Moscow: ZAO «Biznes-shkola «

creation, and the prescriptive part, in which the prescriptions are formulated to certain addressees. The post-text part of the document is important for the addressee as a part that reinforces the legal force of the document, i.e. mandatory execution. Requisites, by performing various functions (metatext, instructing, contact-establishing, intensifying, communicativerestrictive), organize an adequate reading of documents. An important guideline in reading the document is the compositional graphic (sections, chapters, articles) and graphic (numbering, font, italics, indentation, spaces) design elements.

Compositional-graphic tools play an active role in ensuring the coherence of the text, the logical sequence of its fragments. Compositional-graphic division of any text considers the addressee and reflects the desire of the addressee to delimit one information from another, to identify the most important pieces of information in the information plan. Graphical tools allow the addressee to receive additional, hidden, verbally unspecified information, which is contained in the order of paragraphs.

The genres "law", "order", "international agreement" refer to prescription genres (express the semantics of will), their purpose is to regulate the behavior of addressees by means of prescriptions. Prescription activities are carried out as an indication of legal liability that occurs under certain circumstances and conditions (for example, in codes), or as an establishment of order and method for carrying out an action (for example, in a constitution or international treaties), or requiring that in official actions (for example, in orders).

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